

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

Assessment of Water Quality Index of Varun Sagar Lake of Ajmer

Paper Id : 20298 Submission Date : 2025-05-02 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-18 Publication Date : 2025-05-22
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15827824

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Abstract

Varun Sagar Lake is a part of historical, cultural, economic, and recreational life of Ajmer. It is facing multifold pressure due to urbanization, domestic and industrial waste discharge, bathing and washing, agricultural practices and wetland encroachment. The present work is aimed to investigate water quality index of Varun Sagar Lake using water quality index. Nine important water variables were chosen to calculate Water Quality Index (WQI). The collected samples were analyzed for physico-chemical parameters like pH, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Nitrates etc. Different study stations at Varun Sagar Lake exhibited seasonal and inter-site variations in physico-chemical parameters. The mean values of most water quality parameters were significantly higher than the accept limits in the Lake. The cumulative effects of anthropogenic pressure and exerted pollution load from point and non-point sources are affecting water quality of this urban water body. The water quality index value clearly reflected that Water Quality of Lake is "average" and belongs to "C" category of CPCB on 100- point scale. This low value is related to intense human activities and and infusion of pollution from the surroundings in the region. The implementation of WQI is necessary for public and decision makers to evaluate the water quality of the Lake for sustainable management.

Keywords CPCB, Varun Sagar Lake, Urbanization, Water Quality Index (WQI), Physico-chemical Parameters.

Introduction

Water is the main source of life and one of the most important natural resources of the ecosystem. It is essential to manage natural, physical and biological resources for successful economic development and stability of the systems. Upper limit of the population and carrying capacity of the area is set by proper combination of land and water resources in space and time (**Sharma et al. 1999**). Water resources are one of the important life support systems on the earth, covering about 70 percent of the planet, but very small amount (0.00192%) is available and suitable for sustenance of fresh water dependent life (**Cassardo and Jones, 2011**). Sustainable and equitable use of water in the past has been ensured by cultural and social advocacy and adaptation to water availability through water conservation technologies in India. In present scenario, the consequences of population growth, progressive industrialization and urbanization, rehabilitation of arid areas, drive for development and the associated consumerist culture have led to overuse, abuse and pollution of our vital water resources and disturbed the quality and the natural cleansing capacity of water. (**Swaminathan and Manonmani, 1997**). As a result of it, water is considered as the highest risk to the world for future due to increase in demand as well as increase in pollution. On a global scale, total water quantity is not the problem; the main problem is of water availability in the right place at the right time in the right form. The healthiness of the aquatic ecosystem is determined by physical, chemical, and biological

characteristics of the water which strongly influence the aquatic organisms and many of them serve as good ecological indicators of water quality (**Sargaonkar and Deshpande 2003**). Assessment of water quality involves the measurement of a large number of parameters and expressing the quality with respect to particular uses may be a complex issue.

Many methods have been planned and adopted for testing of water quality. As there is lack of consensus among different experts and end users regarding perceptions and interpretation of various parameters of water quality. Therefore, it is necessary to translate water quality data in widely acceptable and unambiguous term. One of the most effective approaches for studying water quality is using of suitable indices which provide single value to the water quality in order to reach comprehensive, dynamic and consistent picture of pollution load of water body (**Prati 1971, Brown et al. 1970**). In general, water quality index is dimensionless number incorporate data from numerous water quality parameters into mathematical equation that rates the healthiness of water body with a single number. That number is placed on a relative scale to validate the water quality in category ranging from very bad to excellent for simplicity and consumers unambiguousness. A number of indices have been developed to summarize water quality data for communication to the general public in an effective way. In this paper a widely used WQI developed by the National Sanitation Foundation (NSF) in 1970 (**Brown et al., 1970**) was used. Essentially, the NSF WQI converts the concentration data for eight analytes into one of five water quality classes, ranging from very bad to excellent. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to enumerate water quality of the Varun Sagar Lake of Ajmer city to achieve water quality status of Lake by using NSF WQI.

Objective of study

The main objective of study is to access the water quality status of Varun Sagar Lake by using Water Quality Index (WQI).

Review of Literature

Singh and Kamal (2014) studied water quality of mining talukas of Goa using WQI and observed highest value of WQI during the monsoon season and the lowest value during the post monsoon season. Most of the water samples were found within Good to moderate categories on the basis of calculated WQI. **Mathur and Gupta (2015)** evaluated the WQI for water in Jaipur, Rajasthan and revealed that WQI is a very helpful tool to evaluate water quality. **Dar et al., (2016)** studied Dal Lake in terms of water quality index and found deterioration in water quality of the Lake due to anthropogenic pressure, siltation, discharge of untreated sewage and encroachment in the catchment results in eutrophication. **Thorvat et al., (2017)** studied Rajaram Lake in Kolhapur city in terms of Water Quality Index and found poor water quality due to various kinds of anthropogenic activities. **Yonnana et al., (2018)** evaluated the water quality of Goro Dong Lake in Numan, Adamawa State, Nigeria by using the Weighted Arithmetic Water Quality Index Method. Results revealed that the observed values of all the parameters were within the permissible limits and the overall Water Quality Index (62.34) indicated that the water quality is poor as evident in high mean value of BOD which is due to excessive anthropogenic activities within its catchment area. **Sudarshan et al., (2019)** carried out a study to evaluate seasonal variation in the physico-chemical parameters of Hebbal Lake, Bangalore using water quality index and found high levels of nutrients and organic load in the inlet region compared to middle and outlets of the Lake. They classified Lake into very poor category on the basis of calculated Overall water quality index. **Weerasinghe and Handapangoda (2019)** assessed the spatio-temporal variability of water quality parameters of East Beira Lake in Colombo, Sri Lanka by using two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's pairwise comparison and found that cumulative effect of anthropogenic activities, Lake morphology and catchment characteristics resulted in the spatio-temporal variability in mean values of TDS, conductivity, salinity, COD, and total Phosphate. **Varol (2020)** evaluated the spatio-temporal variation in surface water quality of the Keban Dam Reservoir in Turkey using trophic state index. They found upstream region of the reservoir was in the eutrophic status, whereas other regions were in the mesotrophic status on the basis of trophic state index values.

Study site: Varun Sagar is freshwater Lake and a recreation centre for the locals of Ajmer. The Lake was constructed by Col. Foy in 1878, and is now under the care of Municipal Council of Ajmer. The Lake is situated at the distance of about 6 Kms. from Ajmer city at longitude 94° 35" and latitude 26°27". The catchment area of the Lake is 28.5 kms. out of which free catchment area is 27.75 sq. kms.

At the time of construction, the capacity of the Lake was 4.245 million cubic meters. The area experiences moderate climate with all four seasons. Here soil is sandy loam to sand clay in texture and low fertile as low in nitrogen and moderate in phosphorous and potassium. The total catchment area of the Lake is 13.44 sq. km. Agricultural as well as Social, economic and ecological scenario of a region is determined by climate of the region which in turn affected by rainfall, temperature and humidity. It is totally rainfed water body and retains water throughout the year. As the low mountain of Aravali unable to meet the proper rainfall so, on an average there are 26 rainy days in a year with annual rainfall of approximately 500 to 600 mm as per the meteorological records. The present study was intended to develop a water quality index for Varun Sagar in order to assess the water pollution status due to anthropogenic meddling.

Methodology

The study was conducted during the period of July 2023 to June, 2024 to explore water quality status of this Lake ecological subsystem. The samples were analyzed immediately for parameters, which need to be determined instantly and rest of the sample was refrigerated at 4⁰C to be analyzed them later. For the estimation of DO and BOD, water samples were fixed at the sites. All the analysis methods followed standard procedures mentioned in "Standard Methods for Examination of Water and Wastewater 20th Edition (1998)," published by APHA, and "Chemical and Biological Methods for Water Pollution Studies" by **Trivedi and Goel (1986)**. Transparency, turbidity, pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), dissolved oxygen (DO), nitrate-nitrogen, Faecal Coliform, biological oxygen demand (BOD) and phosphates were the main parameters analyzed for assessment of water quality status of this Lake. For proper coverage of entire study area and to investigate prevailing physicochemical conditions, four study sites were selected on the basis of anthropogenic load, pollution intake and location-based parameters. To assess water quality of this water body, Brown's water quality index was used. It integrates data generated from physicochemical and microbial analysis after assigning due weights to different parameter (**Table1**). The index can be used to compare different study sites where same objectives and variables are used (**Kankal et al., 2012**). The final calculation of Water Quality Index (WQI) is done by aggregation of subindices using weighted sum index method. The index is given by following formula

$$NSF\ WQI = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i q_i$$

Where, q_i = the quality of the i th parameter (a number between 0 and 100 read from the sub-index graph) w_i = the weight of the i th parameter.

Table: 1. Parameters, Methods and Weights for parameters included in Brown's WQI

Parameters	Analytic method & method No.	Final weight
Faecal coliform density	Membrane filtration & Culture (9222-D)	0.17
Dissolved oxygen	Titrimetric method (4500-O: C)	0.16
pH	pH metric method (4500-H+: B)	0.11
BOD-(5day)	Titrimetric method (5210-B)	0.11
Nitrates	Spectrophotometric method (4500-NO ₃ ⁻)	0.1
Phosphates	Titrimetric method (4500-P: D)	0.1
Temperature	Thermometric method (2550)	0.1
Turbidity	Nephelometric method (2130-B)	0.08
Total dissolved solids	Gravimetric method (2540-B)	0.07

Table:2 Interpretation and designated best end use of water on the basis of WQI quality scale.

WQI Quality Scale	CBCB Class	Interpretation	Use
91-100	A	Excellent	water quality Drinking water source without conventional treatment but after disinfection
71-90	B	Good water quality	Outdoor bathing (organized)
51-70	C	Medium or average water quality	Drinking water source after conventional treatment and disinfection
26-50	D	Fair water quality	Propagation of wild life and Fishries
0-25	E	Poor water	quality Irrigation, industrial cooling, controlled waste disposal

Hypothesis: Ho: The pollution load in Varun Sagar remains within its natural resilience limit and does not affect the water quality to a considerable level spatially as well as temporally within the Lake system. Ha: The pollution load in Varun Sagar is variable beyond its natural resilience limit and affect the water quality to a considerable level spatially as well as temporally within the Lake system.

Table 3: Annual mean values and standard deviation of physico-chemical characteristics of water at Different study stations of Varun Sagar Lake

Parameters	S-1	S-2	S-3	S4	Overall
1. Transparency (in meters)	0.24	0.22	0.28	0.14	0.88
TSI-SD	80.55	81.80	78.33	88.31	61.84
2. Turbidity (in NTU)	17.97	21.65	7.16	41.05	21.95
WQI	5.17	4.80	6.55	3.48	4.77
3. pH (in unit)	8.44	8.39	8.57	8.34	8.43
WQI	7.43	7.58	7.11	7.68	7.45
4. Total Dissolved Solid (in mg/l)	1475	1593	1344	1964	1594
WQI	1.40	1.40	1.40	1.40	1.40
5. Dissolved Oxygen (in % Saturation)	40	38	45	34	39
WQI	5.16	4.77	6.22	4.04	4.96
6. Biological Oxygen Demand (in mg/l)	18.42	28.79	9.22	36.07	23.12
WQI	0.35	0.26	0.43	0.22	0.31
7. Nitrate-Nitrogen (in mg/l)	1.22	1.83	0.61	3.06	1.68
WQI	8.65	8.28	9.03	7.62	8.37
8. Phosphate (Total) (in mg/l)	3.54	5.29	1.76	7.86	4.61
WQI	1.96	1.28	3.15	0.61	1.51
9. Faecal coliform	1570	1649	1286	2107	1653
WQI	2.82	2.79	2.95	2.64	2.80

Result and Discussion

The results obtained by physicochemical analysis of all samples are given in **Table 1** to assess the water quality status of Varun Sagar Lake. Annual mean values of various physico-chemical parameters for different study stations are shown in table no.3

pH: pH is a measurement of the amount of H⁺ ions in water. It can be any number from 0 to 14. pH values fluctuate mostly as a result of component input into water bodies. The majority of biological processes and biochemical reactions are regulated by pH. The pH of the Varun Sagar Lake water was found to be slightly higher in the current study, ranging from **8.34 to 8.57** with corresponding WQI value of **7.68 to 7.11**. **Das and Pandey (1978)** opined that high alkalinity indicates pollution. The pH of a typical eutrophic Lake, according to **Spence (1964)**, ranges from 7.4 to 9.8. The current findings support **Spence's (1964)** statement that the Varun Sagar Lake is eutrophic based on its pH range.

Total dissolved solids: The term solid refers to the matter that remains as residue upon evaporation. Total solids include both dissolved solids and suspended solids. A large number of salts are found dissolved in water. A high concentration of dissolved solids raises the density of water, affects freshwater organisms' osmoregulation, reduces the solubility of gases (such as O₂), diminishes the usefulness of water for drinking, and leads to eutrophication of the aquatic ecosystem. During the investigation, the average TDS was varied from **1344 mg/L (at station-3)** mark as less polluted site to **1964 mg/L (at station-4)**, was marked as more polluted with WQI value of **1.40**. TDS (**Maruthanayagam et al., 2003, Kamath et al., 2006**) showed their maxima in summer. All these parameters were found lower in post monsoon season while they exhibited gradual increasing trend in winter and summer. Throughout the investigation period comparatively low value of TDS was recorded at station III. This is due to negligible disturbance at this station. Whereas, at station IV, higher values indicate maximum disturbance due to human activities. Water body exhibited high values of TDS at the point of discharge of sewage. Also, the number of total solids was found highest during the summer and lowest in winter (**Ugale and Hiware, 2005**).

Dissolved oxygen: All aquatic species rely on dissolved oxygen in water, and it is thought to be the factor that represents the physical and biological processes occurring in a water body. It is necessary for the development and maintenance of life. It has a significant impact on the nature of an entire aquatic environment. The oxygen that a water body obtains comes mostly from two sources: the atmosphere and the photosynthetic activity of chlorophyll bearing plants. The

concentration of dissolved oxygen is also affected by surface agitation caused by temperature, the rate of respiration of living organisms, and the rate of decomposition of dead organic matter. Low temperature in winter contributed rise in DO. In the present study DO% saturation ranged from 34% to 45% with an average of 39%. Maximum value of 45% was recorded in December with corresponding WQI value of 6.22 was marked as least polluted. During summer as a result of high temperature and more oxygen utilization DO was recorded less (minimum 34% at station IV in June with corresponding WQI value of 4.04 marked as most polluted site). **Rani et al. (2004)** reported lower values of dissolved oxygen in summer months due to higher rate of decomposition of organic matter and limited flow of water in low oxygen holding environment due to high temperature. There is an inverse relation between DO and oxygen utilization in terms of BOD and COD. This relation was clearly reported by **Das (2000)** also.

Biochemical Oxygen demand: The aerobic decomposition of organic matter by microbes primarily depends upon the availability of dissolved oxygen. The rate of removal or consumption of oxygen by microorganisms, for this degradation is called the BOD or biological oxygen demand of the water body. BOD gives a complete picture of the nature and extent of pollution and about the water quality (**Kumar and Sharma, 2002**). Oxygen utilization, in the terms of BOD was found maximum in summer season. During the investigation period, BOD values ranged between 9.22 mg l⁻¹ to 36.07 mg l⁻¹ with an average of 23.12 mg l⁻¹, the maximum value (36.07 mg l⁻¹) at site S4 in month of June and minimum value (9.22 mg l⁻¹) at site S3 in month of December was recorded. The Corresponding WQI obtained was in the range of 0.22 to 4.03 with an average value of 0.98, the minimum value (0.22) recorded at site S4 in month of June and maximum (4.03) at site S3 in month of December.

High values of BOD due to accumulation of domestic sewage were also reported by **Mohan et al. (2007)** at Naya Talab, Jodhpur ranging between 88 - 535 mg/l. **Sharma and Gupta (2004)** also found the municipal waste water responsible for maximum organic pollution, resulting in an increased BOD. Same situation prevails at station IV. Regarding BOD values, following ranking order was evident to show pollution load at different stations during the study period. Station IV > Station II > Station I > Station III.

Nitrogen-Nitrate: Nitrate is the highest oxidized form of nitrogen, and in water its most important source is biological oxidation of nitrogenous organic matter. It is an integral component of all essential organic molecules, without whom the existence of life cannot be expected.

During investigation average nitrate values, from **0.61 to 3.06 mg/l** with corresponding WQI value of **9.03 to 7.62** were recorded, indicate higher biological productivity. According to Sylvester (1961) the domestic sewage is mainly responsible for greater concentration of nitrates in fresh waters. **Paulose and Maheshwari (2007)** opined that high nitrate content can be correlated with high rate of organic decomposition while **Chouhan and Sharma (2007)** found agricultural runoff as a main contributor to the nitrate nitrogen in reservoir.

Phosphate: In aquatic systems, phosphorus can be found as free ions, absorbed into sediments and soils, or mineralized in soil, rocks, and sediments. Total average phosphate was also found higher, ranging from **1.76 to 7.86 mg/l** with corresponding WQI value of **3.15 to 0.61**. This confirms the polluted status of Varun Sagar Lake and more deposition of organic matter in it. **Ranga (1995)** also reported high phosphorus-phosphate concentration during monsoon in the water of Anasagar Lake, Ajmer. He emphasized that the difference in phosphate-phosphorus concentration at different stations was due to the addition of detergents and faecal matter of human and avian origin.

Transparency and Turbidity: Natural water in biotic habitats is infested with lot of particulate matter, both in living and nonliving forms which makes the water turbid. Penetration of light is often limited by the suspended materials restricting the photosynthetic zone wherever aquatic habitats have appreciable depth. Turbidity especially when caused by clay and silt particles is often important as limiting factor, conversely when turbidity is a result of living organisms, measurements of transparency become indices of productivity. Transparency was maximum in winter season (**0.28m in December at station III**) with corresponding

TSI value of **78.33** mark as least polluted site) while minimum in rainy season (0.14m in August at station IV with corresponding TSI value of **88.31** was marked as more polluted). It was found negatively correlated with turbidity (Trivedi *et al.* 1987) and nitrate, and positively correlated with pH and DO. As per Khan and Khan (1985) slight to moderate alkaline supports good planktonic growth.

Turbidity was maximum in winter season (**41.05 NTU** in December at station IV with corresponding WQI value of **3.48** mark as most polluted site, while minimum in rainy season (7.16 NTU cm in August at station III with corresponding WQI value of 6.55 was marked as least polluted

Conclusion

In essence the physico-chemical composition of the Lake reveals that it is tending, fast towards 'eutrophism' particularly at station IV. The quality of water is deteriorating day by day due to inflow of domestic sewage, municipal waste, agricultural runoff and effluents of organic waste of animal and human origin into the Lake. Deterioration of water quality and eutrophication are assuming alarming state in Varun Sagar Lake, due to casual attitude of people concerned with development of urban population. Therefore, there is an urgent need of regular monitoring of water quality to govern the status and diverting the city sewage away from the Lake to preserve the flora and fauna of this ecosystem. If waste input is not checked then it will severely impair water dynamics and will cause eutrophication of the entire system. Overall, coordinated efforts of various stakeholders and proper community involvement are the primary needs to restore the ecological subsystem of the Lake and to make it useful for further social and economic exploration. In nutshell, the results depict that the water quality of Varun Sagar Lake rated "Average or medium" and belongs to "C" category of CPCB during the all the month of study and all the stations. Based on these findings, the stations located at the entrance of the pollutants showed lower WQI throughout the study period because of discharge of untreated sewage, rich in organic waste, both from point sources and non-point sources. The water quality index value of this Lake was found much lowered during rainy season. The According to the results of this study, NSF water quality index is a good index for evaluation of the quality of Lake water in which it can be used to determine the water quality at designated stations used for a variety of uses.

Recommendations: In order to assist recuperation of the Lake and to explore it in sustainable manner; immediate priority should be given to identification and abatement of lacuna in existing information and tools failing to conserve the Lake and catchment area. It is necessary to identify the grounds of pollution-source expansion and to check them, to strengthen administrative coordination and explore possibilities of Public Private Partnership (PPP). It is also necessary to prepare action plan on Lake restoration providing sufficient space to beautification in order to develop economic subsystem. A forestation in catchment area, prohibition of construction and garbage disposal near Lake should be enforced. Sewer network and sewage treatment plant should be materialized to limit nutrient entry in the Lake system. Besides source control, some palliative actions should be commenced with prime importance in order to cope up the problem of eutrophication in the Lake system. Continuous water quality monitoring, dredging and de-silting, regulated agricultural practices, promotion of restricted growth of 'nutrient removing plants' like duck-weeds and Eichhornia and their periodical harvesting, bio-remediation and bio-manipulation, rejuvenation of traditional drainage system should be employed. Community based indigenous knowledge system for water harvesting should be materialized to aware and insures involvement of community in efforts for conservation of this natural wealth. But all these efforts will not be motorized until development of proper liaison among different stakeholders. Varun Sagar Lake have high potential for being developed as a city level recreational center and its location and surroundings give an invincible opportunity to develop it as a prominent tourist spot. The Lake periphery should be declared as a 'protected area' to protect the Lake system from unwanted human meddling. It would be better if government recommend the Lake for its declaration as a 'World Heritage Site', keeping more than 500-year-old cultural heritage in mind.

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P: ISSN No. 2231-0045

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025

E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

Periodic Research

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